

Pragmatic goal and context relation

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Аннотация: Анъанавий прагмалингвистикада асосий эътибор сўзловчининг коммуникатив мақсадига қаратилиб, тингловчининг маъно- мазмун шакилланишидаги иштирокига унчалик аҳамият берилмайди.

Нутқий ижодкорлик ва контекст ўзаро боғлиқ ҳодисадир. Контекст унсурлари мулоқот жараёнида ўзаро мослашиши зарурлигини ҳам айтиб ўтади.

Калит сўзлар: семантик, синтактик, монография, дейксис, импликатура, пресуппозиция, дискурс, лисоний, семиотик, психоллингвистика, социоллингвистика, когнитив, антропология, структурализм.

Прагматическая цель и контекстная связь

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Аннотация: В традиционной прагмалингвистике основное внимание уделяется коммуникативной цели говорящего, а участию слушающего в смысло-содержательном формировании не придается большого значения.

Речевое творчество и контекст - взаимосвязанные явления. Также упоминается о необходимости взаимной адаптации элементов контекста в процессе коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: семантический, синтаксический, монография, дейксис, импликатура, пресуппозиция, дискурс, лингвистический, семиотический, психоллингвистический, социоллингвистический, когнитивный, антропологический, структурализм.

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Abstract: In traditional pragmalinguistics, the main focus is on the speaker's communicative goal, and the listener's participation in meaning-content formation is not given much importance.

Speech creativity and context are interrelated phenomena. It also mentions the need for context elements to be mutually adapted in the process of communication.

Key words: semantic, syntactic, monograph, deixis, implicature, presupposition, discourse, linguistic, semiotic, psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, cognitive, anthropology, structuralism.

The leading Uzbek linguists emphasized the need to take into account the "semantic, syntactic and pragmatic" aspects of these phenomena in order to achieve perfection in the study of linguistic phenomena. As a result of following this teaching, a unique school of pragmalinguistics was formed in our country, and during the following years, a number of dissertation studies on the topic were carried out, and significant monographs and educational literature were published (Hakimov 2020). In the mentioned works, problems related to deixis, implicature, presupposition, speech acts and the structure of discourse are being discussed. Also, sometimes the social aspects of pragmatics, the cases that appear in texts of different genres, are studied.

Despite the fact that pragmalinguistics occupies an important place among the fields of linguistics, it is still difficult to reach a consensus about its status and tasks. In particular, theorists of speech acts believe that it is difficult to give a clear explanation of the norm of the concept of pragmatics. According to Leach, pragmatics is the study of how discourse structures convey meaning in certain situations. Another English scientist notes that the object of study of pragmatics is linguistic forms and the relationship of individuals who use them. In our opinion, it is important to pay attention not only to the use of language, but also to the issue of its understanding when defining

the research object of pragmatics. After all, the goal of communication is ensured only if the content intended by the speaker (author) clearly reaches the listener.

When talking about the object of pragmalinguistic research, it is natural to ask whether this direction should be considered as a specific field of general linguistics or whether it is better to leave it within the framework of applied linguistics, which conducts a multifaceted analysis. In our opinion, the sharp separation of different aspects of pragmalinguistics creates a problem. Therefore, the point of view expressed in *Understanding Pragmatics* by J. Verschuren seems promising. The scientist evaluates pragmatics as a science aiming to study "cognitive, social and cultural features of the use of linguistic phenomena in various forms of speech - forms of action."

Linguistics is traditionally divided into such parts as phonetics, phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics. But pragmatics cannot be placed alongside these parts. "Pragmatics is a different look at the phenomena studied by phonologists, morphologists, syntaxists, semanticists, psycholinguists and sociolinguists."

Linguistic phenomenon of any level can be studied from the point of view of its application, therefore, pragmatic content is expressed at all levels. Even at the phonetic level, speakers pronounce sounds differently. Based on these pronunciation norms, it is possible to determine which social group the speaker belongs to. Morphemes, the use of words, also have a pragmatic purpose, and therefore they have different meanings. However, the possibility of consistently and objectively elucidating the contextual basis of the use of language units in the direction of traditional pragmatic analysis is limited. At the level of syntax, there is an opportunity to express a single event by means of different syntactic forms.

Charles Morris, the founder of the field of pragmatics, divided syntax, semantics and pragmatics into separate fields based on three main concepts: a) linguistic sign; b) the thing in reality represented by the sign is an event; c) the person who uses the sign and interprets it. According to the scientist, the interaction of linguistic signs is studied in the framework of syntax, while semantics focuses on the relationship between signs

and the objects named by them, and finally, the object of study of pragmatics is the relationship between signs and their users.

Ravshanki, Ch. These notes of Morris already indicate that the research scope of pragmatics is wide and encourage a comprehensive analysis of the factors that ensure communication.

In fact, as the Uzbek pragmalinguist Sh. Safarov pointed out, "the purpose of communication is not limited to the simple exchange of information, the purpose of information transfer is to influence the partner, to convince him of something, to subdue him, to encourage him to act." In addition, as the semioticians themselves admit, we also know that signs, which are the means of communication, are used by the speaker to express his inclination, liking for someone or something, displeasure, admiration and other emotional feelings. Only when the same aspects of linguistic communication are taken into account, it is possible to imagine that the parts of the semiotic system have a dynamic, dynamic relationship with each other" (Safarov 2008: 54).

From what the scientist said, it becomes clear that the use of language is a specific social character - an action or activity. Therefore, preoccupation with the problem of language use inadvertently leads to the study of the relationship between language and human activity. So, the field of pragmatics actually shows another connection of linguistics. The connection of pragmalinguistics with other multidisciplinary disciplines such as psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, cognitive linguistics, and anthropology is also unique. In pragmatics, a linguistic character - a complete set of actions is studied.

Regardless of how diverse the area of pragmatics and the opinions about its object of study are different, researchers all do not forget to mention the concept of "context" in their descriptions. It cannot be denied that this concept occupies a leading position in pragmalinguistic studies. The concept of context refers to the environment in which the speech structure is formed and includes linguistic, socio-cultural factors. Naturally, the essence of language units is reflected in the situation and environment in which they

are used. A separate word outside the context is only a symbolic sign and does not express a specific meaning, its true meaning depends on the context in which it occurs. It is for this reason that two terms occupy the main place in the definitions given to pragmatics. One of them is "information" and the other is "context". We observe this, for example, in the definition given in Alan Cruz's book:

Context is a complex phenomenon that is directly related to meaning or content studied in the fields of linguistics and literary studies. The phrase "any word used in a new context is a new word" (Firth 1957: 190) once said by the exponent of structuralism means that the meaning of a lexical unit is the result of its use in a particular environment. Context can be linguistic and situational.

Normal communication always takes place in a certain environment, and this is directly reflected in the activity of using language and understanding the content. In other words, the alternative and appropriateness of this or that speech act is determined in relation to the context of speech communication. A speech structure without an alternative to the context, the situation, loses its meaning. Therefore, in the analysis of content and pragmatic alternatives, linguists turn away from the grammatical structure of the structure and turn to non-linguistic indicators. Accordingly, the context plays an important role in the analysis of dialogues in the artistic text.

Researchers dealing with the problem of context note that this phenomenon is made up of various factors. In his above-mentioned book, J. Först considers context as consisting of text and situation (Firth 1957: 190). It is customary to divide contexts into three types, namely linguistic, cultural and situational contexts. Linguists based on J. Forst's theory focus on the relationship between language and society when describing the context. For them, changes in context cause changes in language, and also context is a specific semiotic structure that expresses the set of meanings of the semiotic system that organizes culture (Halliday 1978). Researchers who follow this idea of the London Functional School captain try to describe the context in relation to the situation that occurs outside the text.

M. According to Holliday, linguists conducting research on the issue of context should focus on generalizing the characteristics of all contexts rather than on specific situations. He advocates focusing on the role of contextual factors in the expression of meaning. This indicates that the contextual factors in the discourse affect the meaning of the text, the interpersonal meaning and the original meaning. These three types of meaning, in turn, influence the linguistic choices made by the speaker and the information conveyed, its modal content (Halliday 1978). It is clear from this that the context plays an important role in the human activity of knowing the world

the context requires interaction of activating factors in different ways. In other words, the context is a specific world related to the performance of speech activity. Consequently, in addition to deictic (space-time) indicators, direct linguistic

environment and paralinguistic means, there are other situations that indicate the determination of meaning. These are, for example, the scope of communication, personality of interlocutors, environment and socio-cultural, historical environment. There are different reasons for the ambiguity in the interpretation of the contextual event. First, real context and related factors are often confounded; secondly, in the traditional interpretation of the context phenomenon, the concept of "common knowledge" has an abstract appearance, not concrete; thirdly, the mental state of speakers, which affects speech creativity and pragmatic content, is not taken into account. This, in turn, causes the context to be perceived as a stable, static phenomenon. However, the pattern of communication-activity and the environment and context in which it occurs are expected to change. Therefore, it is necessary to recognize that communication is a process oriented towards the creation and perception of meaning, and that the context in which it takes place adapts accordingly. The dynamic nature of the context creates conditions for its participants to correctly understand the meaning of the linguistic means used. In this case, the transmitted information is divided into two types: in one, the transmitter considers the receiver already aware of it, and in the second part, the information is considered new. However, "the status of a piece of information can change during discourse, information that is already "new" in one sentence, becomes "old" in another" (Cook 1994: 36).

However, in the dynamic process of communication, some elements (including prior knowledge, time and place of communication) may remain static, but others are constantly in motion. During the interaction, the level of common knowledge of the interlocutors increases, and at the same time they understand each other.

J. Verschueren takes a somewhat different approach to the phenomenon of context in his book *Understanding Pragmatics* mentioned earlier (Verschueren 1999: 75-114). First of all, he divides this phenomenon into two types, that is, linguistic and communicative. The first of them includes the method of communication, continuity,

cohesion and intertextuality, while the communicative context consists of the material, social and intellectual worlds of language users (Verschueren 1999: 76).

The scientist puts the speaker and the listener in the most important place, because the material, social and mental world becomes an indicator that determines the context only due to the activities of the participants of the communication. The effect of speech creativity and the relationship of its understanding is related to the closeness in the level of knowledge of these individuals.

It is known that in traditional pragmalinguistics, the main attention is focused on the communicative goal of the speaker, and the listener's participation in the meaning-content formation is not given much importance. J. Verschurin, unlike others, emphasizes that the role of the listener is special in this, and notes that understanding the content of the speech structure is a dynamic thinking activity. In the process of communication, the listener is an active participant who contributes to the creation of content. It forms the meaning that corresponds to the communicative purpose of the speaker. This indicates the importance of the listener's correct understanding of the speech structure in order to achieve the communicative goal. Therefore, while commenting on the concept of context, J. Verschurin considers it necessary to mention the interaction between the speaker and the recipient of information, the ability to adapt their speech act to the situation.

The scientist recognizes that the context determines the choice of linguistic units, noting that the realization of the pragmatic goal is adapted to a certain context. Therefore, speech creativity and context are interrelated phenomena. Understanding activity is also dynamic. Dialogue participants can understand the content of the speech structure in different ways while performing the actions of forming, proving and transmitting linguistic information in a certain situation. Such a different interpretation creates a new situation. Meanwhile, J. Verschuren relates context to the process of communication in action and notes that it changes during this process. The scientist also mentions the need

for context elements to be mutually adapted in the process of communication. This requires the analysis of the factors that ensure adaptation.

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